

Book Chapter:

Closing the Funding Gap: Biodiversity Finance Mechanisms

Julia Qian Mao,
Lund University, Sweden
Julia_qian.mao@svet.lu.se

Abstract

The Kunming-Montréal Global Biodiversity Framework, adopted at COP15, establishes a clear mandate to mobilize funding from diverse sources to address the escalating biodiversity crisis. Despite growing awareness and commitment to biodiversity conservation, a substantial financing gap persists, hindering efforts to protect and restore ecosystems effectively. This chapter provides an in-depth examination of financial mechanisms designed to bridge this gap, presenting both established and emerging strategies. Drawing on recent studies quantifying the biodiversity funding gap, the chapter synthesizes global and national insights to illuminate the scale of the challenge. It underscores the urgent need for innovative financial mechanisms to mitigate biodiversity loss and ensure the long-term sustainability of natural ecosystems. Applying an updated framework, the chapter categorizes and analyzes biodiversity finance mechanisms in the context of their evolution and growing innovation. It examines traditional approaches such as domestic government funding, international grants and transfers, and conservation trust funds, as well as novel mechanisms like payments for ecosystem services, biodiversity offsets, and ecological fiscal transfers. The chapter also emphasizes the interplay between biodiversity and climate, highlighting opportunities for synergy across environmental themes.

This chapter reveals a transformative shift in biodiversity finance, moving from reliance on external funding and public budgets to market-based and self-generated mechanisms. Simultaneously, it emphasizes the critical role of public policy and government in enabling and regulating these approaches, even within market-driven models. By offering a comprehensive overview of biodiversity finance mechanisms, this chapter lays the groundwork for subsequent discussions on specific financial instruments, including biodiversity bonds, credits, insurance, and certification schemes. It serves as an essential resource for policymakers, investors, conservation practitioners, and researchers seeking to advance biodiversity conservation through innovative financial mechanisms.

Key words: Nature conservation, innovative funding, policy and market instruments, financial instruments

13.1 Background: Funding Gaps and Calls for Actions

Biodiversity, the variety of life on Earth, underpins critical ecosystem services such as clean water, pollination, and climate regulation, which are essential for human well-being and economic prosperity (Arlaud et al., 2018). However, global biodiversity is in a state of unprecedented decline, with ecosystems facing threats from habitat loss, pollution, climate change, and overexploitation (IPBES, 2019). Recognizing this crisis, the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), was established to promote the conservation of biological diversity, the sustainable use of its components, and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from the use of genetic resources (CBD, 2011). At the fifteenth meeting of the Conference of the Parties (COP 15) to the CBD, the Kunming-Montréal Global Biodiversity Framework (KMGBF) was adopted, envisioning “living in harmony with nature by 2050” and outlining transformative missions to be achieved by 2030. The framework calls for urgent and transformative action across all levels of government and civil society to halt biodiversity loss. It includes four long-term global goals for 2050 and 23 action-oriented targets for 2030 (CBD, 2022). Notably, the fourth goal emphasizes securing adequate financial resources to close the biodiversity financing gap and align financial flows with the framework’s objectives and the 2050 Vision. Target 19 specifically aims to mobilize USD \$200 billion annually by 2030 from domestic, international, public, and private sources (CBD, 2022).

There is growing consensus within the international community on the urgency of scaling up biodiversity finance while redirecting capital away from activities that harm biodiversity. Implementing the global biodiversity framework requires this dual approach (OECD, 2020). An expanding body of literature (Seidl et al., 2020; Waldron et al., 2013, 2017) and reports from international organizations (Deutz et al., 2020; OECD, 2020; Tobin-de la Puente & Mitchell, 2021; UNEP, 2023) have emphasized the need to increase funding for biodiversity conservation. These studies have quantified biodiversity financing gaps and assessed existing mechanisms at global (Deutz et al., 2020; OECD, 2020; Seidl et al., 2020) and national levels (Berghöfer et al., 2017; Cruz-Trinidad et al., 2024), offering valuable insights into the scale of the current challenge.

At the global level, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2020) estimated that annual global biodiversity finance averaged USD \$78–91 billion between 2015 and 2017, equivalent to just 0.1% of global GDP. Of this, public domestic expenditure contributed USD \$67.8 billion, international public expenditure contributed USD \$3.9–9.3 billion, and private expenditure accounted for USD \$6.6–13.6 billion. In stark contrast, annual government expenditures potentially harmful to biodiversity were estimated at USD \$500 billion, highlighting the urgent need to realign financial flows toward biodiversity-positive investments. Deutz et al. (2020) estimated that current spending on biodiversity conservation ranges between USD \$124–143 billion annually, against a total estimated need of USD \$722–967 billion per year, leaving a financing gap of USD \$598–824 billion. Tobin-de la Puente and Mitchell (2021) also underscored a significant increase in estimated biodiversity financial flows compared to earlier estimates of USD \$52 billion annually (Cranford et al., 2012). Seidl et al. (2020) estimated that global public biodiversity investments increased to an average of USD \$121 billion annually from 2008–2017, equivalent to 0.19–0.25% of global GDP. Additionally, the proportion of biodiversity spending in total public spending has grown.

At the national level, Berghöfer et al. (2017) highlighted significant funding gaps across eight countries with whom Germany has biodiversity finance-related bilateral technical cooperation, emphasizing the need for innovative mechanisms tailored to specific contexts. Similarly, the

United Nations Development Programme's (UNDP) Biodiversity Finance Initiative (BIOFIN) has conducted comprehensive reviews across 41 countries, examining current expenditures, financing gaps, and future biodiversity finance plans. This work is now expanding to 91 additional countries with Global Environment Facility (GEF) support (Cruz-Trinidad et al., 2024), offering detailed insights into country-specific biodiversity finance landscapes.

Given the increasing understanding of biodiversity financing challenges, the center of discussions about them has naturally shifted toward filling funding gaps through innovative mechanisms. According to Anyango-van Zwieten (2021), the most pressing themes in biodiversity finance literature are funding shortages, inefficient allocation, and the need for innovative mechanisms. Key contributors to underfunding include inadequate public budgets, inefficient resource allocation (Anyango-van Zwieten, 2021), and limited private sector involvement (UNEP FI & UNDP BIOFIN, 2023; zu Ermgassen et al., 2024). While it is critical to understand the emerging innovative financial mechanisms, it is equally important to expand the concept of “innovation” from only financial mechanisms to include efforts to address conservation cost drivers and improve spending effectiveness (Berghöfer et al., 2017).

Following this review of the biodiversity financing gap and calls for innovative mechanisms, this chapter begins with a discussion on typologies of biodiversity finance mechanisms and their associated instruments (Section 13.2). It then explores the current landscape of biodiversity finance, encompassing traditional and emerging mechanisms (Section 13.3). The chapter concludes by identifying trends in evolving biodiversity finance mechanisms, emphasizing the role of public policy, and highlighting key opportunities for further development (Section 13.4).

13.2 Understanding of Biodiversity Finance Mechanisms

Early research on biodiversity finance mechanisms predominantly focused on financing protected areas (PAs). A notable contribution is from Emerton (2006), which provided a global review and assessment of financial instruments for PAs, proposing a typology of financing mechanisms categorized into three primary types based on how funds are raised and utilized.

- **External Funding Mechanisms:** These mechanisms focus on attracting and managing external financial flows, including government and donor budgets, NGO grants, and private or voluntary donations from both domestic and international sources.
- **Incentive Funding Mechanisms:** These mechanisms are designed to incentivize conservation activities through cost and benefit sharing, investment and enterprise funds, fiscal instruments, and arrangements that support private or community management of PA resources and facilities.
- **Market-Based Mechanisms:** These mechanisms employ market-driven charges for PA goods and services, such as resource use fees, tourism charges, and payments for ecosystem services. (Emerton, 2006)

Building on Emerton's framework, Berghöfer et al. (2017) expanded and refined this typology to include financing mechanisms for both PAs and their surrounding landscapes (Fig. 13.1). The updated typology retains Emerton's core logic, classifying mechanisms based on whether funding originates from private or public sources, and whether it is self-generated or dependent on external flows.

Fig. 13.1 A typology of financing mechanisms for PAs as well as in surrounding landscapes. Source: Berghöfer et al. (2017)

Meyers et al. (2020) further advanced the classification of conservation finance mechanisms, introducing a comprehensive taxonomy aimed at systematically organizing all known mechanisms and strategies. This taxonomy employs a two-tiered structure (Fig. 13.2).

The first level comprises broad categories such as return-based investment, economic instruments, grants and other transfers, business and market mechanisms, public financial management, risk management, and financial efficiency. The second level provides detailed narrative descriptions of each mechanism within these categories, offering a thorough overview of the diverse range of known mechanisms (Meyers et al., 2020). Notably, the taxonomy includes mechanisms related to risk management and financial efficiency, reflecting the continued advancement and diversification of conservation finance mechanisms and strategies. Meyers et al. (2020)'s taxonomy reflects a strong characteristic of pragmatism, designed to be both relevant and actionable for policymakers and practitioners. This practical orientation enhances its utility in addressing real-world challenges in biodiversity conservation financing.

A Taxonomy of Conservation Finance Mechanisms

A. Return-Based Investments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microfinance • Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Investing and Crowdfunding • Angel Investing, Incubators and Venture Capital • Private Equity • Debt: Leasing, Bank Loans, Notes, and Trade Finance • Capital Markets • Sustainable Investment Strategies
B. Economic Instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmentally Related Taxes • Fees and Charges • Tradable Resource Use Permits • Fines and Penalties • Compensation and Offsets • Deposit-refund Schemes • Environmentally Motivated Subsidies
C. Grants and Other Transfers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Official Development Assistance (ODA) • Private and Corporate Philanthropy • Remittances • Conservation Trust Funds / Environmental Funds
D. Business and Markets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supply Chain Resilience • Conservation Businesses • Corporate Social Responsibility and Sustainability • Voluntary Offsets
E. Public Financial Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public Fiscal Planning, Budgeting and Disbursement • Fiscal Transfers • Government Grants • Reforming Harmful Subsidies • Earmarking Revenues for Nature
F. Risk Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insurance Products • Pay for Success • Blended Finance
G. Financial Efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management Effectiveness • Public Private Partnerships • Integrated Accounting • Mainstreaming Biodiversity in Development

Fig. 13.2 A taxonomy of conservation finance mechanisms. Source: Meyers et al. (2020, p. 6)

The UNDP BIOFIN has played a pivotal role in developing and implementing biodiversity finance mechanisms globally. BIOFIN adopts the term “finance solution” to describe a set of activities — often involving multiple mechanisms — designed to address specific biodiversity finance challenges. These solutions aim to achieve financial, policy, and institutional outcomes to mitigate biodiversity loss drivers (Cruz-Trinidad et al., 2024). BIOFIN categorizes financing mechanisms into different types, including policy-focused, market based, fiscal, debt or equity, and risk-related types. BIOFIN further identifies four potential finance results for biodiversity finance solutions:

Deliver Better, Generate Revenues, Avoid Future Expenditures, and Realign Expenditures (Fig. 13.3) (Cruz-Trinidad et al., 2024).

Fig. 13.3 The four finance results from BIOFIN finance solutions. Source: Cruz-Trinidad et al. (2024)

Biodiversity financial mechanisms in this chapter are conceptualized as broad channels, structures, and systems designed to direct financial capital flows towards conservation, restoration, and sustainable use and management of biodiversity.

These mechanisms differ from financial instruments, which refer to specific tools or contracts operating at the transactional level, such as grants, debt, and equity. Financial instruments act as the foundational components of financial mechanisms. For instance, a biodiversity financial mechanism may employ a combination of grants, loans, and equity to achieve its objectives.

13.3 Landscape of Biodiversity Finance Mechanisms

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the biodiversity finance mechanisms landscape, focusing on major types, their current state, and emerging trends. Rather than delving into the specifics of each mechanism, which has been thoroughly addressed in prior studies (Meyers et al., 2020; OECD, 2013, 2021, 2024b; Pirard, 2012; Pirard & Lapeyre, 2014; Ring & Barton, 2015; Ring & Schröter-Schlaack, 2011), it utilizes an updated framework to categorize and analyze biodiversity finance mechanisms in the context of their evolution and growing innovation.

Building on the foundational typologies proposed by Emerton (2006) and Berghöfer et al. (2017), this framework categorizes biodiversity finance mechanisms along two dimensions: funding generation and funding sector (Fig. 13.4). The horizontal axis of Fig. 13.4 distinguishes between mechanisms based on how financial resources are generated. Toward the “self-generated” side are mechanisms that generate financial resources internally, often through market-based approaches like payments for ecosystem services (PES), tourism fees, or biodiversity credits. Toward the “external funding” side are mechanisms that rely on external financial flows, such as grants, government transfers, and philanthropic contributions. The vertical axis differentiates between mechanisms based on their primary funding source. Towards the “public” side are mechanisms driven by government budgets, taxes, subsidies, or fiscal policies, while towards the “private” side are mechanisms supported by private sector investments, corporate social responsibility initiatives, or voluntary contributions.

Fig. 13.4 Framework for categorizing biodiversity finance mechanisms, adapted from Emerton (2006) and Berghöfer, et al. (2017). Source: Author (2025)

This framework provides a dynamic and adaptable approach to understanding the cross-dimensional characteristics of biodiversity finance mechanisms and their relevance to specific country contexts. The strength of this updated framework lies in its capacity to illuminate the cross-dimensional characteristics of financial mechanisms while remaining adaptable to diverse country contexts. Moreover, it effectively captures the dynamic evolution of the biodiversity finance landscape, characterized by increasingly overlapping public and private funding sources and a notable shift toward self-generated financial mechanisms.

The following section starts with traditional finance mechanisms, which primarily rely on external funding flows from both the public and private sectors and then transits to the opposite end of the spectrum, exploring self-generated financial mechanisms. The evolving landscape of biodiversity finance underscores the importance of adaptive frameworks that can capture the dynamic interplay between funding generation and sectoral contributions.

13.3.1 Domestic and International Public Funding Mechanisms

Domestic Public Expenditure

According to OECD (2020), the global average annual domestic public expenditure on the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity between 2015 and 2017 was USD \$67.8 billion. This figure significantly surpasses international public expenditure (USD \$3.9–9.3 billion) and private expenditure (USD \$6.6–13.6 billion), making domestic public expenditure the predominant source of biodiversity funding (OECD, 2020).

Domestic public expenditure here refers to financial resources provided within a country by national and subnational governments, public agencies, and public financial institutions. This category of funding is broad and often interacts with other mechanisms, such as fiscal policies. It forms the backbone of biodiversity finance, serving as the primary financial resource for implementing a country's National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP) and fulfilling national and international biodiversity commitments. This foundational mechanism can be leveraged to mobilize additional resources from private sector investments and international funds. Through strategic allocation of domestic budgets, governments can address biodiversity challenges while fostering synergies with broader development objectives.

As highlighted earlier, the UNDP BIOFIN initiative has supported 41 countries in developing and implementing biodiversity finance plans. A critical component of this process involves conducting biodiversity expenditure reviews (BERs). To facilitate the calculation and tracking of domestic public biodiversity expenditures, BIOFIN developed the GLOBE Taxonomy, a comprehensive framework that categorizes biodiversity expenditures and provides standardized biodiversity attribution rates (Cruz-Trinidad et al., 2024).

Despite its importance, domestic public expenditure is often constrained by a country's fiscal capacity. Larger economies typically invest more in biodiversity, both in absolute terms and as a percentage of GDP and national budgets (Seidl et al., 2021). In contrast, developing countries, which often face resource limitations and competing demands, may struggle to allocate sufficient funding for biodiversity. Recurring budgets for activities such as managing protected areas are particularly vulnerable in the absence of clear economic returns (World Bank, 2021). Funding challenges are evident in regions like Africa (Lindsey et al., 2021) and Latin America (Bovarnick et al., 2010), where resource constraints hinder the ability to meet biodiversity commitments. For these regions, international financial mechanisms play a particular crucial role.

International Finance Mechanisms Under and Beyond the CBD

The GEF serves as the institutionalized financial mechanism of the CBD, playing a pivotal role in supporting developing countries and economies in transition to fulfill their biodiversity commitments. It functions as a multilateral family of funds dedicated to addressing “biodiversity loss, climate change, pollution, and supporting land and ocean health,” which includes the GEF Trust Fund, Global Biodiversity Framework Fund (GBFF), Least Developed Countries Fund (LDCF), Special Climate Change Fund, Nagoya Protocol Implementation Fund, and the Capacity-building Initiative for Transparency Trust Fund (GEF, 2024b).

GEF funding is provided by country donors, with the council-approved funds distributed through 18 GEF agencies, such as the Asian Development Bank, the International Fund for Agricultural Development, International Union for Conservation of Nature, UNDP, United Nations Environment Programme, and World Bank Group. These agencies partner with government bodies, civil society organizations, private sector entities, and research institutions to execute biodiversity projects and programs in recipient countries. Financial contributions from donor countries are administered via trust funds managed by the World Bank, acting as the GEF Trustee. The Trustee mobilizes resources through a replenishment process every four years (GEF, 2024a).

Over its tenure, the GEF has provided more than USD \$26 billion in financing and mobilized USD \$149 billion for country-driven priority projects (GEF, 2024b). Specifically, it has allocated more than USD \$5.2 billion for biodiversity conservation, leveraging USD \$13.4 billion in co-financing

to implement more than 1,500 projects across 158 countries (CBD, 2024). In its current GEF-8 phase, at least 60% of investments are estimated to be biodiversity-relevant. As of mid-2024, GEF-8 had approved investments exceeding USD \$3 billion, leveraging over USD \$19 billion in co-financing to the KMGBF through program lines within GEF-8, including Biodiversity Focal Area strategy, GBFF, GEF-8 Integrated Programs, International Waters Focal Area, LDCF, Non-grant Instrument, and Small Grants Programme (CBD, 2024).

In 2023, the GEF established the GBFF to support the implementation of KMGBF. This fund complements existing mechanisms, scaling up biodiversity financing through predictable and timely resource flows. The GBFF allocates 36–39% of its resources to Least Developed Countries and Small Island Developing States, with 25% directed through international financial institutions, and an aspirational target of 20% allocated to Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities by 2030 (CBD, 2024). The first programming tranche of USD \$211 million — based on pledges from donor countries such as Canada, Germany, and Japan — was allocated in early 2024, followed by additional contributions from Luxembourg and New Zealand. By mid-2024, 22 out of 70 grant requests were approved, involving 24 countries (CBD, 2024).

Beyond the GEF and GBFF, more international funds operate outside the CBD’s authority. These include the Critical Ecosystem Partnership Fund, Global Fund for Coral Reefs, ASN Biodiversity Fund, Lion’s Share Fund, LEAF Coalition, Legacy Landscapes Fund, and Biodiverse Landscapes Fund (CBD, 2024). Many of these funds address biodiversity and climate change simultaneously, reflecting the interconnected nature of these challenges. Climate change, recognized as one of the five direct drivers of biodiversity loss, exacerbates biodiversity decline, while biodiversity degradation further intensifies climate risks. Consequently, major international funds such as the Green Climate Fund and the Land Degradation Neutrality Fund often finance both biodiversity and climate initiatives.

However, biodiversity finance lacks a dedicated global tracking system, such as one similar to Climate Fund Update’s global climate finance architecture, which regularly monitors international climate funds and tracks financing flows (Watson et al., 2024). Establishing a similar system for biodiversity finance would provide invaluable insights into the global finance architecture and inform strategies for closing biodiversity financing gaps.

Funding Channeled through Development Finance

According to OECD (2020), Development Assistance Committee (DAC) members are the largest providers of bilateral development finance for biodiversity. Biodiversity-related development finance from DAC members grew from USD \$9.5 billion in 2015 to USD \$12.1 billion in 2022, with an annual average of USD \$9.7 billion, representing 7% of total development finance flows. This growth reflects increasing commitments by DAC members to biodiversity-related development finance pledges. Five DAC members — Germany, France, the European Union (EU), the United States, and Japan — account for at least 70% of biodiversity-related official development finance (ODF), with the EU and its DAC member states collectively contributing 68% of total biodiversity-related ODF (Fig. 13.5).

2011-2020, bilateral commitments, USD million, 2020 prices, full values

Fig. 13.5 Major donors in the area of biodiversity-related development finance. Source: OECD (2023)

Most biodiversity finance provided through ODF is allocated as grants, particularly in Oceania and Africa, while debt instruments are more common in Europe, Asia, and Latin America (Fig. 13.6). Additionally, non-DAC countries have emerged as significant contributors to biodiversity development finance through South-South and triangular cooperation mechanisms. These include Arab Gulf nations such as Saudi Arabia and United Arab Emirates, and emerging economies like Brazil, Chile, Colombia, India, Indonesia, and South Africa (OECD, 2023, 2024a).

2015-22, USD, full values

Notes: ODF: official development finance; LAC: Latin America and the Caribbean. Africa and Asia receive most DAC member biodiversity-related ODF. Financial instruments represented include: grants (e.g. standard grants); debt instruments (e.g. standard loans, reimbursable grants and other debt securities); and equity (e.g. common equity and shares in collective investment vehicles). About 24%, or USD 2.3 billion, of biodiversity-related ODF falls into the “unallocated” by region category, i.e. it is not earmarked to a country or region, and so has not been included in this analysis.

Fig. 13.6 DAC members’ biodiversity-related official development finance by region. Source: OECD (2024a)

Multilateral development banks (MDBs) also play a critical and complementary role in biodiversity finance (OECD, 2020, 2023, 2024a). Institutions such as the Asian Development Bank, Inter-American Development Bank and the World Bank support biodiversity-related projects through concessional loans and grants, often accompanied by technical assistance. These concessional instruments help de-risk projects, enabling the mobilization of co-financing from private sector actors (OECD, 2023). In cases of commercial feasibility, MDBs can also offer commercial loans and equity investments, similar to those provided by private financial institutions. This flexibility allows MDBs to transition toward more self-generated and market-based mechanisms as bankable biodiversity projects are identified and developed.

Conservation Trust Fund

Conservation trust funds (CTFs) deserve special emphasis as an important type of traditional biodiversity finance mechanism, closely connected to the funding approaches discussed earlier. Emerging in the early 1990s to manage capital from debt-for-nature swaps (Bladon et al., 2014), CTFs have evolved to become principal financing mechanisms for protected areas, with strong financial sustainability (Berghöfer et al., 2017).

CTFs are legally independent institutions that mobilize, manage, and allocate financial resources to ensure long-term, sustainable funding for biodiversity conservation. To date, over 70 CTFs have

been established globally (Bladon et al., 2014). These funds typically take the form of endowments, sinking funds, revolving funds, or hybrids of these structures (Fig. 13.7). They play a pivotal role as conduits for revenues generated by mechanisms such as PES, user fees, Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation Plus (REDD+) programs, and biodiversity offsets (Bladon et al., 2014; Spergel & Taïeb, 2008).

	PROS	CONS
<p>Endowment fund</p> <p>Where the financial assets of a fund are invested and only the income from this investment is used to finance activities.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suitable for PA and national park financing, which require a long-term source of financing. • Can cover a CTF's basic operation costs. • Can be useful to leverage additional sources of funding. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ties up substantial amounts of resources with relatively low returns. • Takes time to start producing income. • Least attractive to donors.
<p>Sinking fund</p> <p>Where activities are financed using both principle and investment income over a fixed period of time (usually 6-15 years), or until the fund sinks to zero.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suitable when large amounts of money are required on a one-time basis. • More attractive to donors as they like to see the effects of money being spent. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of permanence.
<p>Revolving fund</p> <p>Where a fund is replenished or augmented on a continuous basis, for example through earmarked taxes, user fees, and so on.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can last in perpetuity if the source is financially sustainable. • Can cover a CTF's basic operation costs. • Can connect ES beneficiaries with providers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If used in isolation, withdrawal of the source of replenishment could cause the collapse of the fund.

Fig. 13.7 Summary of common types of CTFs and their pros and cons. Source: Bladon et al. (2014)

The funding sources for CTFs reflect their integration within the broader biodiversity finance architecture. GEF and bilateral aid agencies collectively account for approximately 75% of total funding, while contributions from corporate entities, non-profits, and philanthropic organizations continue to grow (Spergel & Taïeb, 2008). This highlights CTFs' dual role as recipients of external funding and as mechanisms to distribute resources generated through other financial instruments.

The design and implementation of CTFs vary significantly depending on the political and legal contexts in which they operate. While their flexibility enables customization to address specific challenges, it also underscores the importance of aligning their structures with local needs and priorities. As such, CTFs exemplify the intersection of traditional and innovative finance mechanisms, bridging funding sources and conservation outcomes in ways that are adaptable to evolving biodiversity finance landscapes.

13.3.2 Private External Funding Mechanisms from Philanthropy and Business

Private external funding mechanisms, driven by philanthropy and corporate social responsibility have emerged as critical components of biodiversity finance, complementing public sector efforts and market-based approaches.

Philanthropy as a Catalyst for Conservation

Philanthropic contributions have historically played a significant role in biodiversity conservation, but the current scale and pace of these contributions are unprecedented (Beer, 2023). For instance, private donors committed USD \$5 billion to advance global biodiversity targets under the KMGBF (Gruby et al., 2023). However, academic research on the role of environmental philanthropy in financing biodiversity conservation remains limited (Gruby et al., 2023).

Conservation philanthropy refers to voluntary contributions to biodiversity conservation (Ramutsindela et al., 2013). This funding is often flexible, enabling initiatives that may lack immediate financial returns but are critical for long-term ecological and societal benefits. Philanthropy financial mechanisms encompass various financial instruments, including donations from high-net-worth individuals, grants from foundations and other philanthropic organizations, and crowdfunding from individuals (Gallo-Cajiao et al., 2018; Seidl et al., 2024).

Philanthropy is evolving in both financial mechanisms and functions. Some philanthropic fundings have expanded from the traditional “trust-based philanthropy” model to so called “dollars for policy” approach where international foundations leverage funding commitments to influence state-led conservation governance (Beer, 2023; Gruby et al., 2023; Rogers, 2015). A notable example is Project Finance for Permanence, an innovative philanthropic mechanism that secures long-term political and fiscal commitments in exchange for substantial conservation funding (Beer, 2023). While such approaches enhance the effectiveness of conservation efforts and catalyze additional funding from governments, they also grant philanthropic entities greater control over state conservation governance.

Business Contributions to Biodiversity Finance

The private sector is increasingly recognizing the value of biodiversity and integrating biodiversity considerations into corporate strategies. Business contributions to biodiversity finance take various forms, ranging from donations and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) funds to direct investments and partnerships to other innovative financial instruments.

Many corporations support biodiversity conservation as part of their CSR commitments, allocating fundings for ecosystem restoration, community engagement, and sustainable resource use. In India, CSR spending has been made a statutory obligation for companies under the Companies Act, 2013 (Section 135), indicating a systematic effort to mandate corporate contributions to biodiversity financing mechanisms (National Biodiversity Authority, 2019).

As a market-led, voluntary initiative, Task Force for Nature-related Financial Disclosure (TNFD) brings in new rationale for the businesses sector to integrate biodiversity into its financial decision-making. The TNFD framework enables businesses and financial institutions to assess their dependence and impact on nature, identify nature-related risks and opportunities, and align their strategies with broader biodiversity goals (TNFD, 2023). This approach not only enhances corporate responsibility but also underscores the strategic value of biodiversity for risk management, new business opportunities, and responding to investor pressure.

CSR funding can intersect with other biodiversity finance mechanisms, such as biodiversity offsets or biodiversity credits. Companies, particularly those in sectors like mining, energy, and infrastructure, may have the need of purchasing credits to offset their ecological footprint. Voluntary biodiversity footprint compensation is driven by corporate shareholders and stakeholder pressure (Biodiversity Credit Alliance, 2023). With the regulatory environment increasingly aligning with the global shift toward a nature-positive economy, companies may opt to purchase

biodiversity credits as a means of regulatory compliance (Biodiversity Credit Alliance, 2023). This interaction demonstrates how businesses contribute to biodiversity finance through voluntary or compliance-driven mechanisms.

In addition to traditional CSR contributions, businesses are increasingly leveraging innovative market-based instruments to finance biodiversity-related activities. Instruments such as green bonds and biodiversity bonds are gaining traction among large corporate issuers. As of 2023, the corporate sector represents 57% of the issuance of green issuance, with non-financial corporate issuers account contributing over half of this share (Climate Bonds Initiative, 2025). By adopting these mechanisms, businesses transition from being mere external funders to active participants in self-generated financial mechanisms, fostering a more integrated approach to biodiversity finance.

13.3.3 Innovative Self-Generated Finance Mechanisms

Driven by calls to increase private sector investment (Barbier et al., 2018; CBD, 2022; Credit Suisse et al., 2014; Deutz et al., 2020), the evolution of biodiversity finance has witnessed growing emphasis on self-generated financial mechanisms.

Market-based mechanisms, in particular, have gained significant attention, with numerous studies systematically examining their diverse forms and applications. Scholars have conducted systematic reviews on market-based funding initiatives, as well as developed comprehensive lexicons categorizing market-based instruments for biodiversity and ecosystem services, encompassing (Bosshard et al., 2021; Pirard, 2012; Pirard & Lapeyre, 2014). These instruments vary in their connection to regulatory and policy frameworks, including tax policies and other public interventions. In addition to broad typologies, extensive research has also focused on specific market-based or blended financial mechanisms. Key examples include PES, biodiversity offsets, debt-for-nature swaps, impact investments, and blended finance models (Bull et al., 2013; Christiansen, 2021; Jayachandran et al., 2017; Koh et al., 2019; Mancini et al., 2024; McGowan et al., 2020; Muradian et al., 2010; Nedopil, 2023; Niner & Randalls, 2021; Pascal et al., 2021).

Meanwhile, public sector-led self-generated mechanisms, such as biodiversity taxes and fines, fiscal reform, and Ecological Fiscal Transfers (EFTs), remain essential components of the biodiversity finance landscape (Cruz-Trinidad et al., 2024; OECD, 2013, 2024b; Ring & Barton, 2015; Ring & Schröter-Schlaack, 2011). The following sections highlight three market-based self-generated financial mechanisms and one public sector-led mechanism to demonstrate the innovative potential of self-generated financial mechanisms.

Biodiversity Offsets

Biodiversity offsets are novel mechanisms designed to compensate for the unavoidable loss of biodiversity caused by development projects. The goal of biodiversity offsets is to achieve “no net loss” or “net gain” of biodiversity by creating, restoring, or protecting biodiversity elsewhere to balance the ecological impact of a certain project.

While biodiversity offsets have gained increasing interest in recent years, they remain a contentious tool within conservation circles (Bull et al., 2013). Within the mitigation hierarchy, biodiversity offsets are considered a last resort, to be employed only after efforts to avoid, minimize, and restore biodiversity impacts have been exhausted. As financial mechanisms, biodiversity offsets represent structured economic instruments aimed at channeling resources into conservation efforts through compensation schemes.

Deutz et al. (2020) estimated that finance mobilized by biodiversity offset mechanisms ranges from USD \$6.3–9.2 billion per year. According to OECD’s Policy Instruments for the Environment (PINE), as of 2014, nine countries had biodiversity offset programs encompassing a total of 17 active biodiversity offset schemes (OECD, 2024b). Although often identified as market-based mechanisms, Koh et al. (2019) argue that biodiversity offset mechanisms can be categorized into three institutional types: “Public Agency,” governed directly by government regulations; “Mandatory Market,” regulated and supervised by the state; and “Voluntary Offset,” driven by corporate social responsibility initiatives without legal obligations.

Institutional frameworks and government involvement play a decisive role in shaping biodiversity offset mechanisms, influencing their operational structures and levels of commodification. Unlike pure market-driven tools, biodiversity offsets predominantly rely on cost-based pricing models, which emphasize the expenses of conservation actions rather than assigning a direct monetary value to biodiversity itself (Koh et al., 2019). It underscores the hybrid nature of biodiversity offsets, blending regulatory oversight with market-based principles to achieve conservation goals effectively.

Payments for Ecosystem Services

Payments for ecosystem services (PES) represents an innovative mechanism that incentivizes landowners to manage their land or resources in ways that conserve or enhance vital ecosystem services. These services include benefits provided by nature, such as clean water, carbon sequestration, biodiversity conservation, and soil fertility. At its core, PES establishes a voluntary, market-based mechanism where users or beneficiaries of ecosystem services, such as governments, corporations, or communities, provide compensation to those who maintain, protect, or restore the ecosystems delivering these services.

Although comprehensive data on PES programs remains limited, the OECD (2024b) notes a rising trend in their adoption. Its PINE database indicates that as of 2024 28 countries have implemented active PES programs, covering a total of 51 initiatives globally (OECD, 2024b).

While widely recognized as a market-based mechanism, PES is influenced by the institutional and political contexts in which it operates. Muradian et al. (2010) highlight the importance of these institutional dynamics, noting that PES mechanisms are rarely standalone solutions. Ring and Barton (2015) further emphasize that PES should be understood within the context of a broader policy mix. The “rules-in-use” framework, encompassing scope, choice, payoff, and boundary rules, defines the eligibility criteria, required actions, and incentive structures of PES contracts. These rules interact with other policy instruments, leading to synergies, redundancies, or conflicts. To maximize its effectiveness, PES should be thoughtfully integrated into broader governance frameworks, accounting for land-use dynamics, institutional design, and the complex interplay of policies and actors (Ring & Barton, 2015).

Ecological Fiscal Transfer

Ecological Fiscal Transfer (EFT) is a relatively new financial mechanism that has begun to scale significantly in recent years (Seidl et al., 2021). EFTs involve the transfer of public revenue between governments within a country based on ecological indicators. By compensating subnational governments for the costs of conserving ecosystems, EFTs create incentives for greater ecological conservation and sustainable management of natural resources. These transfers can be vertical, from higher- to lower-level governments, or horizontal, between governments at the

same level. EFT can be general-purpose, allowing recipient governments to allocate funds freely, or specific-purpose, earmarked for ecological projects like reforestation or water treatment (Busch et al., 2021).

A review by Busch et al. (2021) on established EFTs in Brazil, China, France, India, and Portugal as well as emerging or proposed EFT schemes in ten additional countries, highlights the rapid growth of this mechanism. The annual total volume of EFTs increased from USD \$0.35 billion in 2007 to USD \$23 billion in 2020, reflecting its expanding role in biodiversity finance.

Despite their potential, the success of EFTs lies on several key factors, including ecological monitoring systems to ensure accurate performance measurement, governance structures that promote accountability and equitable distribution of funds, and allocation formulas that account for socio-economic disparities and ecological priorities. These elements are critical for maximizing the ecological and fiscal benefits of EFTs while ensuring their sustainability and fairness.

As more nations explore and implement EFTs, this mechanism offers a compelling pathway to align fiscal policies with global biodiversity goals. By incentivizing conservation through financial rewards, EFTs not only address funding gaps but also promote long-term sustainability and resilience in ecological systems.

13.4 Discussion and Conclusion

The global landscape of biodiversity finance is undergoing a profound transformation, marked by an increasing emphasis on innovative, self-generated mechanisms. This shift reflects a gradual departure from dependence on external funding and public budgeting and a growing focus on market-based and blended approaches aimed at the enhanced sustainability of funding supply. Biodiversity, long regarded as a public good primarily funded through public expenditure, is now at the center of redefined state-market dynamics and evolving public-private relationships. This reconfiguration holds a new paradigm for designing mechanisms to address the complex challenges of biodiversity conservation.

Innovative financial mechanisms, such as biodiversity offsets and biodiversity credits, have garnered substantial attention in recent years. However, it is essential to prioritize the suitability of mechanisms over pursuing trendy but potentially impractical solutions. Establishing new financial mechanisms often involves creating institutions, developing skills, and forging novel partnerships. Before embarking on the development of new mechanisms, it is important to explore opportunities for enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of existing ones (Berghöfer et al., 2017).

Governments and public policies remain pivotal in the operation and success of many market-based mechanisms, such as PES and biodiversity offsets (Koh et al., 2019; Muradian et al., 2010). Public policy plays a dual role, on the one hand supporting these mechanisms by creating enabling environment and conditions, regulating markets, and de-risking nature-based projects, and on the other hand limiting mechanisms with poor coordination and policy or regulatory uncertainties (Sumaila et al., 2021; zu Ermgassen et al., 2024). Therefore, discussions on market-based mechanisms must be connected to regulatory and policy frameworks in specific institutional and contextual realities.

Collaborative funding models and the integration of multiple financial mechanisms are increasingly recognized as effective strategies to enhance biodiversity financing. For instance, Conservation Trust Funds often require co-financing through domestic budgets as a condition for support, fostering greater government ownership of conservation initiatives (Bladon et al., 2014). Similarly, philanthropic capital has adopted innovative mechanisms such as Project Finance for Permanence, leveraging substantial political and fiscal commitments from states in exchange for philanthropic contributions (Beer, 2023). While these approaches offer opportunities to coordinate mechanisms and catalyze additional funding, they also introduce new power dynamics, granting private funders greater influence over government biodiversity and fiscal policies.

A critical pathway for advancing biodiversity finance lies in identifying and promoting the co-benefits of biodiversity conservation across sectors such as climate finance and infrastructure. Aligning financial mechanisms under different environmental themes can amplify synergies and maximize returns on investment. For example, integrating national action plans under frameworks such as the CBD, United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD), and United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) can align restoration targets, deliver multiple benefits, and optimize funding efficiency. Infrastructure investment presents another promising opportunity for synergy. Nature-based infrastructure (NBI) is up to 50% cheaper than traditional “gray” infrastructure to provide the same infrastructure service, while offering 28% better value for money (IISD, 2021). With global infrastructure investment needs projected to reach USD \$94 trillion by 2040 (CBD, 2024), exploring financial mechanisms for NBI holds immense potential for both biodiversity and finance outcomes.

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